

A Study on Market Prospect of Chicory at Hyderabad Metro Kiosks

BVDS Sai Pavan Kumar ^{1*}, T. Madhuri Reddy ¹, Prof M. Seema ¹, Dr . P. PrasadaRao¹

Abstract: Hyderabad is one on the global cities which is known for its rapid infrastructural grown and development in field of information technology. [1] Currently Hyderabad is having an easy mobility for its residents and tourists from all over the world. The project called Hyderabad metro rail, which is developed by Larsen and turbo company and started its operations in 29 November 2017 .[2] The metro stations are equipped with kiosks which will help the transistors be rejuvenated while on transit. [3] These kiosks are strategically planned in terms of infrastructure, space and the kind of food they offer to their customers. The kiosks will be replacing the use of coffee on the whole with a resembling product- CHICORY that has better health benefits when compared to coffee. Chicory is not only healthier but also has no caffeine content in it. Moreover, it's way cheaper than coffee. Through this paper , we try to enlighten the advantages of chicory over coffee not only in Hyderabad metro kiosks but also in everyday life. The current paper is a well conducted research on the use of chicory in the metro stations and the benefits it has over consuming coffee. There are various objectives that are achieved through a rigorous market research including financial viability of chicory.

I. Introduction

Hyderabad Metro Rail (HMR) is a rapid transit system, currently being used in the city of Hyderabad. It is in Secant Operational model.[4] It is being implemented entirely on public- private partnership (PPP) basis, with the state government holding a minority equity stake.[5] Which is developed by an Indian multi-national conglomerate headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra- Larsen and Turbo. The first phase of the project which is spread across 30 kilometres from Miyapur to Nagole was inaugurated by honourable prime minister Shri Narendra Modi on 28th of November 2017 , this first phase includes 24 . This is the longest rapid transit metro line which was opened in one go in India . this project is estimated to cost ₹ 18,800 crore (US\$2.6 billion).[6] As of February 2020, there are about 490, 000 passengers who use the Metro per day. Trains are crowded during the morning and evening peak hours[7] A ladies only coach was introduced on all the trains from 7 May 2018. [8] New products in the market do not always flourish. Sometimes the attributes of the product make it flourish and sometimes it doesn't. The scope of this paper is majorly related to the idea of using Chicory in Hyderabad Metro Kiosks in order to have a change in the lifestyle of the people in Hyderabad. Chicory has a number of advantages over Coffee which is the main point that the study keeps in account. The current paper would provide a number of advantages of Chicory and how revolutionary it will be, if offered at places like kiosks in the metro station. The paper would provide innovative ways of launching Chicory in the market. Also determining the consensus of people who would try Chicory in the kiosks of the metro stations. The paper would also like to make a financial viability of Chicory in the market.

The study was undertaken in order to understand the usage of Chicory- a new product with similar attributes of coffee. Coffee is more like a need to most of the people but at the end is not healthy because of high content of caffeine. Chicory is a similar product with better advantages and nutrients and tastes similar to Coffee. The paper will help us find out if people are ready to accept a healthier product which is cheaper and beneficial

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To understand the market potential of Chicory at Hyderabad Metro Stations.
- 2) To have a comparative study of Chicory and Coffee.

A Study on Market Prospect of Chicory at Hyderabad Metro Kiosks

- 3) To suggest innovative ways of bringing Chicory in to the market at effectively launching it at Hyderabad Metro Stations.
- 4) To understand the financial viability or the pricing strategy of Chicory.

III. Research methodology

The research methodology consists of three major components

A] Research design The research used for this study is descriptive in nature. This design is adopted to know the attitude of the respondents regarding usage of Chicory at various Hyderabad Metro Stations. B] Sample design: The respondents were selected by random sampling. The survey was conducted in a period of 45 days. C] Sample size The sample size was taken from survey which includes 100 people from different parts of the city.

IV. COLLECTION OF DATA

In the dealing with any problem it is often found that data at hand are inadequate, and therefore it becomes necessary to collect data that are appropriate. These are several ways of collecting the appropriate data, which defer considerably in context of time and other resources. Here for the purpose of study two kinds of data will be used.

> Primary Data

> Secondary Data

A] PRIMARY DATA The primary data is that which is directly collected from the customers and consumers, and thus happens to be original character. With reference to this study data was collected through It is a fresh data, which was collected from the customers having discussion and interaction and filling up of questionnaire.

B] SECONDARY DATA

Various reports, text books constitute the secondary data.

The survey has been conducted using Online Google forms from 100 respondents .The respondents have been classified mainly in to three age groups AG1, AG2 and AG3. GP1 has age group of 16-35 years consisting of mostly students and earning people in their early part of career.GP 2 has age group respondents 36-50 years mostly well settled earners. There will be variation in shopping behaviour and preferences for online shopping for the two age groups.GP 3 having age group of 50 consisting of well settled people and near to their retirement and above .[10]

V. Results and analysis

The results are presented as overall respondent's answers along with specific age group choices.

The general data concerning the survey has been shown in table 3.1. Out of 300 respondents 53% are male and 47% are female respondents. The respondents are mixture of various categories in terms of age, marital status, occupation and earnings per month, place of residence as well as nationality.

TABLE 3.1: shows the general data concerning the survey

SNO	parameter	Characteristics	Percentage	
1	gender	Male	53	
		Female	47	
2	Place of residence	metropolitan	68	
		urban	18	
		rural	14	
3	Marital status	married	48	
		unmarried	52	
4	Monthly earnings	<10,000	9	
		<25,000	13	
		<50,000	36	
		<75,000	32	
		76,000 & above	10	

5.1 Frequency of visiting metro travel

The frequency of visiting metro travel during the last one year is shown in figure 3.1. 47% of respondents are travelling in metro on regular basis. Still there are almost 15% of people Travelling rarely travel on metro. Even the GP3 are travelling in metro, this indicates metro has been successfully reaching all the people irrespective of their age group

Figure

5.1 shows the frequency at which people travel in Hyderabad metro rail

5.2 Awareness of the product “Chicory”

Figure 5.2 shows percentage of people who are aware of chicory

Among all the respondents 52 percent of respondents are aware of chicory while 48 percent of respondents are not aware of it . This shows that there is only half of the people are aware so it’s primarily important that the awareness of chicory should be developed among the people .

Preference of Coffee over Chicory

Chicory is a healthier alternative of coffee . which would taste same as coffee . when we look at the data more people from the group AG-2 prefer mostly coffee . but surprisingly people from age group of AG-1 who are future of the country are preferring chicory more than coffee . this shows young people are more health conscious than other age group people . the another probable reason for it is the people from the groups of AG-2 and AG-3 have habituated to coffee so they dislike the chicory

Graph 5.1 , shows the preference of coffee over chicory with respect to age groups

5.3 Knowledge of the health benefits of Chicory

Chicory a product known for its benefits is barely known to people. People have no clue about the benefits which it provides. The benefits are amazing and they not only are financially beneficial but also have health benefits. So 14% people know about Chicory’s benefits and 82% people aren’t aware of the benefits of Chicory and the rest are unsure.

5.4 Chicory - one product many benefits

Chicory as a product helps with stress relief. Chicory has an amazing benefit which coffee doesn’t. Only 22% are aware of this benefit of Chicory while 78% people say they don’t know it helps in releasing stress. Chicory as a product helps with weight loss. Chicory has an amazing benefit which coffee doesn’t. Only 18% are aware of this benefit of Chicory while 82% people say they don’t know it helps in weight loss. People who weren’t aware of the benefits of Chicory also don’t know that it’s cheaper than Coffee. 85% people are such who don’t know

that Chicory is cheaper and only 15% have an idea about the price at which this product is sold in the market Graph 5.2 represents how many people are aware of benefits of chicory

5.5 Health or taste

33% people prefer health benefits over pleasing their taste buds. 24% people were particular about soothing their taste buds and are aware of missing out on the benefits that Chicory provides and are ready to give up on it while 43% people are confused and unsure whether they must please their taste buds or have benefits to their health. when we analyse according to the age groups AG-1, AG-2, and AG-3. The people from AG-1 and AG-3 mostly prefer health over their taste buds , but AG-2 people show an inclination towards their taste buds this can be attributed to their life style or the work pressure and stress they have since most of the people from this area falls under the working group

Graph 5.3 shows preference toward health and taste

5.6 Chicory served in fancy cups Fancy cups are no fantasy for 33% people. No matter what the product is served in, it is seen that these people are not at all interested in consuming the product. 37% people look interested in having Chicory in fancy cups while the rest are unsure about consuming Chicory in fancy cups.

Consuming Chicory if it comes for free with other products

43% people are interested in having Chicory for free when it comes with other product. 26% people say they aren't interested in consuming Chicory even if it comes for free and 31% people are unsure about consuming it even if it comes for free . even if we analyse by the age groups people of AG-1 and AG-2 are attracted and want to consume if it is given free with any other product where as people from the group AG-3 does not get offend by this they don't like to have chicory even if it is given for free .

Conclusions

The market potential of Chicory in Hyderabad Metro Kiosks is high. The term Chicory is not known to a lot of people and nor is its benefits known to the people. Passengers who would use Hyderabad Metro Station would buy Chicory if it is offered. According to the analysis, about 18 % would try chicory if it is offered at Hyderabad Metro Kiosks. Most of the people are not just addicted to caffeine but also prefer its taste only. But they aren't aware that Chicory is a product which tastes similar to coffee and doesn't have caffeine which when consumed in excess quantity acts like poison to the body. People would stick to their traditional coffee brands at home and wouldn't welcome Chicory at home and wouldn't make it a part of their lives. There are 53% people who prefer consumption of coffee at home. If chicory is introduced in the kiosks only 37% people would try it at least once and about 36% people are unsure about trying it. 82% people aren't aware of the benefits of Chicory over Coffee. People aren't aware about the health benefits including stress reduction and weight reduction which are key benefits of consuming Chicory. Chicory isn't just beneficial when it comes to health but also is very viable financially. Most of the people aren't aware that Coffee is costlier than Chicory it is seen that people would be interested in consuming Chicory if it is served in fancy cups and not in regular cups. This shows that Chicory has a lot of potential if it is sold in fancy cups. If Chicory is given for free, more than 40% would consume it. Even if coffee is priced rupees 20, more than 40% would consume it and if Chicory is priced at rupees 10, about 50% would buy it. This shows that people would buy a product looking at its price and not just its attributes. more than 75% people are eager to try Chicory at least once in their lifetime. This shows how welcoming the product will be once it is brought in to Hyderabad Metro Kiosks and how hit this product will be once it is launched.

Suggestions

To have Chicory its market share, the product must not be priced more than rupees 10. The product would be liked extremely if it is served in fancy cups and not just in normal cups. Chicory will be liked if customer testimonials are convincing. Chicory shouldn't be placed alongside tea to have it differentiated. Chicory must be offered for free for the first one year to have the people get used to its taste and understand its benefits. The kiosks walls should be painted with the benefits of Chicory on it to educate people who aren't aware of the term. The ticket counters must have pamphlets describing the benefits of Chicory. Chicory must be served in cups which are printed with its benefits and these cups must have three languages: Hindi, English and Telugu. The kiosks must provide cards or coupons which would earn those points and get them a free ride. For example: for every 50 cups, one ride free. The kiosks must use recyclable cups and not plastic cups and plates. Create sample sizes of products and offer them to those who review and give feedback for Chicory Create Blogs and testimonials

References

- [1.] Economic Analysis of Hyderabad Metro Rail Project by Bharath. K published in international journal of technology in volume 5 issue 2 2.
- [2.] TECHNICAL ANALYSIS OF THE HYDERABAD METRO RAIL PROJECT by Nagarjuna Pilaka K published in international journal of technology in volume 5 issue 2.
- [3.] END USER IMPACT OF METRO RAIL SERVICES IN HYDERABAD a report by Tata Institute of Social Sciences Hyderabad published in the year 2017.
- [4.] Limao N. and A. J. Venables (2001), Infrastructure, Geographical Disadvantage and Transportation Costs, Policy Research Working Paper.
- [5.] Hyderabad metro rail an important PPP project published in nbm & cw in 08-2016.
- [6.] Redesigning a people friendly published in metro India on 13-06-2015.
- [7.] The new life in metro published in economic times on 07-06-2015.
- [8.] Taking hyderabadis to better work published in the financial express on 10-2018.
- [9.] World award for hmr published in Hyderabad chronicle on 31-03-2013.
- [10.] S.P GUPTA AND M.P. GUPTA "Business statistics" SULTAN CHAND & SONS publishing, Indian printed. New Delhi, 2018. 19th edition